

Early Electronic Screen Exposure and Autistic-like Symptoms**Atul Jain Singhai¹, Amarjeet Singh Chhabra², Ajay Bhatt³, Ajay Soni⁴**¹3rd Year PG Resident, Dept of Physiology, MGMMC, Indore²Associate Professor, Dept of Physiology, MGMMC, Indore³ Professor & Head, Dept of Physiology, MGMMC, Indore⁴Assistant Professor, Dept of Physiology, MGMMC, Indore

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Abstract:

Prevalence autism spectrum disorders (ASD) has been on rise, but many studies suggest over-diagnosed. Currently, children have more access to electronic media on the daily basis than those of previous generation. Some studies suggest that increases screen time is associated with melanopsin-expressing neurons and decreasing gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) neurotransmitter, and thus results aberrant behavior, decreased cognitive, and language development. Early exposure of electronic media in early life (< 2 years old) gives an impact on language, but it still inconclusive. We made a study aiming at revealing the impact of early exposure of electronic screen on language development and autistic-like behavior. Results showed that children who spent viewing ≤ 3 hours per day had language delay and short attention span, while children who spent viewing ≥ 3 hours per day had language delay, short attention span, and hyperactivity. While we found that more than a half of children (66.6%) had no parents-child interaction during the exposure, speech delayed and short attention had been reported in all cases, and hyperactivity was found in 66.6% children.

Keywords: Screen exposure, speech delay, short attention span, hyperactivity.

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Introduction

Prevalence of using electronic screen media was high among children below 3 years and tends to increase within a decade. Some studies suggest that increased screen time in young children is associated to negative health outcomes such as decreased cognitive ability, impaired language development, mood, and autistic-like behaviour including hyperactivity, short attention span, and irritability. Currently, children worldwide spend more time with electronic screen media compare to children which previously more socially engage. The first exposure has been found in much younger age and, more overly, parents actively persuade them to use electronic screen media as a companion to entertain and to keep them occupied, therefore, the parent can freely work on their own. Surprisingly, almost all parents proudly reported that their child aged below 2 years has been able and enjoy electronic media in regular basis.

Early exposure to screen can cause neurochemical and anatomical brain changes. Reduced melatonin concentration has been found significantly in a group of individuals who were exposed to screen [3]. Neurotransmitter deficiency like dopamine, acetylcholine, gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA), and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) was observed in study on internet-addicted urban left-behind

children which may cause a spectrum of aberrant behaviour phenotype [4]. Takeuchi *et al.* [5] found that there is a positive effects of screen exposure on regional grey matter volume and white matter volume in the brain that may correlates with verbal competence, aggression, and cognitive abilities.

The disruption of those biological daily light-dark rhythms from environment can increase depression-like behaviour and cognitive function through melanopsin-expressing neurons [6]. Light input is detected by and signalled to relevant brain regions through retinal ganglion cells (RGCs). The majority of RGCs signal light to thalamic nuclei and visual cortex for image visual function, the minority, called intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs) for non-image visual function expresses the photopigment melanopsin. Melanopsin expression ipRGCs distribute to multiple brain regions including suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN), ventrolateral preoptic area (VLPO), and limbic regions in order to regulate circadian rhythms, sleep, cognitive function, and mood.

Methodology

We made an autism risk factor study in residential societies in Indore. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM)-5 had been

administered by experienced paediatricians to diagnosed autism spectrum disorders (ASD). Children who met criteria of ASD, had an IQ under 70, and had syndromic intellectual disabilities (ID) were excluded, only Children who had autistic-like behaviour were included. Intellectual Quotient (IQ) was measured using Wechsler Scale. Parents of children who had scored above 70 who signed the consent form was administered structured interview of electronic screen media exposure questionnaires to access time of first exposure, spent time viewing, and parent-child interaction. Chief complaint was obtained during interview and confirmed by experienced paediatricians. Risk factors of language delayed *i.e.*, family history of language delayed, low birth weight, neurological disorders, ear problems, severe toxic exposure, chronic medical illness, severe infectious diseases were obtained using questionnaire. Ethical Clearance was obtained from the Scientific committee of MGM Medical College Indore.

Results

35 children who met criteria with autistic-like behaviour were included (15 males, 20 females; aged 44- 78 months). All children had speech delay as a chief complain, and among them one case was non-verbal. The time of first exposure was very early, all had exposure before 2 years old, more overly,

two cases had been exposed before the age of first. Parents reported having interaction with children

during the exposure only in three cases, while the majority of cases (66.6%) there was no interaction during the exposure. Aberrant behavioural phenotypes were observed including short attention span was found in all cases and hyperactivity in the majority of cases (66.6%). Children who spent viewing ≤ 3 hours per day had language delay and short attention span, while children who spent viewing ≥ 3 hours per day had language delay, short attention span, and hyperactivity.

In all cases, the first exposure was started before 2 years old, and the intention of exposure was very high in the majority of cases (≥ 3 hours/day). Chonchaiya et al. found that children who started watching television before 12 months and watched more than 2 hours a day were six times more likely to have language delays [2]. Electronic screen stimulation in early stage leads dysregulation and disorganization of various biological systems. Escalation of stimulation especially in early stage, will also influence other function, and language is the function that mostly affected [9]. Recently, Fisher introduced a new term of electronic screen syndrome (ESS), an unrecognized disorder associated with exposure of electronic media and mental health symptoms *i.e.* mood, anxiety, cognition, behaviour, and social interaction due to hyperarousal. (Unpublished data, Martin H Fisher, Electronic Screen Syndrome: An unrecognized disorder).

Domain 1: Screen time exposure and home media environment
What is the frequency of watching television in a typical week?
Duration of watching television on a typical working day?
Duration of watching television on a typical holiday?
Does the child watch television supervision frequency by an adult?
What is the frequency of using smartphone in a typical week?
Duration of using smartphone on a typical working day?
Duration of using smartphone on a typical holiday?
Does the child us smartphone supervision frequency by an adult?
What is the frequency of watching laptop/ computer in a typical week?
Duration of watching laptop/ computer on a typical working day?
Duration of watching laptop/ computer on a typical holiday?
Does the child watch laptop/ computer supervision frequency by an adult?
Do you have any rules regarding when, where, what & how to watch digital screen?
Average duration of screen time per day of the caretaker
Domain 2: Level of physical activity
Average duration of outside play per day on working/ school days
Average duration on holidays of outside play per day
Domain 3: Media behaviors of the child
The child uses digital media gadgets for completing homework assignments online
The child uses video calling applications to talk to the family/ friends
The child uses digital media gadgets for learning poems, rhymes, alphabets etc.
The child uses digital media gadgets to learns math's, numbers, tables
The child uses digital media gadgets to recognize shapes/ sounds/ colors
The child uses digital media gadgets to learns various sciences online

The child uses digital media gadgets to learns to draw/ write
The child plays videogames on digital media gadgets
The child uses digital media gadgets to watches stories
The child uses digital media gadgets to watch adult programs (soap)
The child uses digital media gadgets to learns letters, words, vocabulary, language online
Digital media gadgets to watch random things for enjoyment (music, advertisements, click photos etc)

Conclusions

This study found that more than a half of children (66.6%) had no parents-child interaction during the exposure, speech delayed, and short attention had been reported in all cases, and hyperactivity was found in 66.6% children. Previous studies shown negative associations between times spent viewing TV and the range of cognitive outcomes in young children including attention, intelligence, and future educational attainment. A longitudinal study in 2004 found that the more TV watched by infants (aged 1-3), the more likely they were to have attention problems. In addition, poor quality of interactions with parents combine with screen excessive use may have negative effects on children's health and development, parent-child interactions were found had positive impact on language development especially word learning and retention. Studies in rodent revealed the behavioural changes occurred because ipRGCs project to the brain regions involved in mood. Bedrosian TA and Nelson RJ summarizing the effect of aberrant light and mood disorders through ipRGC projections to brain regions involved in emotions, and also an effective source for suppressing nocturnal melatonin that can lead sleep disruption.

Study Limitation

An important limitation is the lack of a control group that would help us evaluate the effect of screen exposure and whether autistic-like behaviour is indeed increased in children due to excessive screen exposure.

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